

Functional Time Series Models for Dynamic Updating Prediction of Sugar Production

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ABSTRACT

Functional data analysis has been widely applied across various fields, yet its use in predicting crop production outcomes, particularly sugar production in Sub-Saharan Africa, remains limited. Traditional crop forecasting relies heavily on conventional time series models, with minimal integration of dynamic updating techniques for functional time series. This study proposes three dynamic updating methods —Ridge Regression, Penalized Least Squares, and Local Polynomial Regression —to enhance sugar production forecasting in African countries. Monthly sugar production data were structured into N-yearly curves, allowing for real-time prediction updates during the current season. Model performance was evaluated against the auto-ARIMA algorithm, revealing that at least one proposed functional time series method outperformed ARIMA across all datasets. Specifically, Ridge Regression provided the best estimates for Eswatini. While the Penalized Least Square and Local Polynomial Regression were the most effective for Kenya and South Africa, respectively. Overall, dynamic updating proved beneficial in refining initial predictions and enabling timely adjustments to industry strategies. The study advocates integrating dynamic updating with traditional forecasting approaches to enhance prediction reliability, particularly for volatile agricultural datasets.

INTRODUCTION

The world has embraced cloud computing, and better computers with more storage capacity emerge every year, making it possible to collect data more frequently. The resulting time series contains observations recorded with high frequency and provides more information about the phenomenon under study but is difficult to analyze, especially when the data has multiple seasonality. Using conventional time series approaches, such data is modeled as a univariate time series, arranging the observations in chronological order. Also, the data can be modeled as a multivariate time series. For example, daily data collected over several years can be concatenated to have a single observation corresponding to a whole year's data. However, the main challenge with the multivariate approach is the increased dimensions. Attempts to minimize the dimensions by reducing the frequency of recording observations to weekly or monthly will often result in information loss.

In functional time series (FTS) modeling, each data point is considered as a curve or function instead of a scalar or vector

quantity. For every time set, say year t , the data is transformed to a functional time series $Y(t, x)$, such that there is a function $Y(., x)$ for every t with $Y(t, i/d) = X(t, i)$. Basically, x is a continuous domain, $i = 1, 2, \dots, d$, and d is the total number of discrete time points. In essence, each observation is regarded as a function of time (Ramsay and Silverman, 2005). According to Ramsay and Silverman (2005), FTS enables the modeling of seasonal data with complex patterns that cannot be adequately catered for by conventional time series approaches. FTS allows flexibility by capturing the entire functions over time and can explicitly capture temporal dependencies to improve the representation and forecasting of irregular patterns in data (Hormann and Kokoszka, 2012). Dynamic updating of FTS models involves breaking down a sequential univariate time series into several equispaced curves that enable forecasting without removing the seasonal fluctuations in data. New observations are added to the most recent curve to improve the forecast without overhauling the original model. Recent studies (Shang and Hyndman, 2011;

Elias et al., 2022) have shown that dynamic updating methods provide more accurate predictions than most of the traditional time series models. Shang and Hyndman (2011) proposed four dynamic updating methods, including the ordinary least squares (OLS), ridge regression (RR), block moving (BM), and penalized least squares (PLS). All, except the ordinary least squares approach, performed better than the ARIMA models, effectively minimizing the approximation error and consequently improving the accuracy of predictions.

PLS technique is widely accepted in forecasting when the distribution of the underlying dataset cannot be described exclusively. The approach has been effectively adopted in several sectors, such as agriculture to predict forest cover (Lazaridis et al., 2011), in meteorology to forecast El Nino occurrence (Shang and Hyndman, 2011), and in population studies (Kihara, 2013), among others.

This study also models sugar production in African countries using two other functional time series methods, ridge regression (RR) and local polynomial regression (LPR). RR helps to overcome the challenge of a higher error margin associated with linear regression (LR). LR has zero bias but suffers from high variance, hence RR is expected to provide more accurate long term forecasts. LPR, on the other hand, substantially reduces both design and boundary biases, hence suitable for the study.

1.1 Functional Principal Component Analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a crucial tool in multivariate data analysis that has been in use since the beginning of the 20th century. PCA seeks to determine the key components that cause the patterns and variation in a dataset. The key strength of PCA is its ability to find a reduced dimensional representation while preserving most of the information contained in the original variables. However, the application of PCA is restricted to datasets where observations are equispaced. Also, the sample size must be larger than the variable count to achieve the desired results. These conditions may not be achievable in multivariate data from some sectors, such as astronomy, genomics, biostatistics, and many others (Shang, 2014). On the other hand, functional Principal Component Analysis (FPCA) is an extension of Principal

Component Analysis (PCA) that analyzes functions instead of vectors or scalar quantities. When the dataset contains covariates that are considered as smooth functions, FPCA becomes a plausible choice because it overcomes the “curse of dimensionality,” which PCA suffers. As dimensionality grows, the volume rises even faster, making the available data points sparse and insufficient. FPCA obtains uncorrelated PC functions, maximizing variance for each particular component (Ramsay and Silverman, 2005).

1.2 Sugar Production in Sub-Saharan Africa

Sugarcane is a perennial crop, but sugar production seasons differ across countries. In East Africa, for instance, milling activities continue all year round from January to December,

except in Tanzania, where the off-crop season runs from March to May. The sugar production season in southern Africa is mainly from April to December. There are little to no sugarcane harvesting and milling activities during the off-crop, and factories take the time to do machinery maintenance and cane development. In the absence of an off-crop season, such as in Kenya and Uganda, individual millers can allocate a month or two within the year for factory maintenance.

The climatic conditions and geographical location determine the milling season in each sugar producing country in sub-Saharan Africa. Except in places with no off-crop season, manufacturers prefer to harvest and crush cane when it is dry and sunny and stop the factories when it is rainy and cloudy. Within the equatorial region, sunshine hours are evenly spread throughout the year, making it realistic to produce cane sugar all year round.

Low temperatures and solar radiation contribute to low sucrose content in cane, which is not ideal for maximizing sugar production and returns (Zhao et al., 2023). Rainfall amounts and distribution are also crucial to the sugarcane yield. Sugarcane needs more water at the growth stage and less humidity towards maturity for favorable yields. Therefore, the total amount of sugar produced in a given surface area is a function of the cane yield and the sucrose percentage.

On a wider scale, the total quantity of cane sugar produced in a given country would also depend on the milling capacity and efficiency, the level of farm mechanization and inputs, the area under cane, and the cane price, among other factors. Investment in the sugar milling sector in any country is likely to drive additional crop cultivation, especially where each new factory develops its nucleus estate. Higher cane prices also attract more people to sugarcane farming, leading to an increase in acreage, while reduced cane prices could make growers shift to planting competing crops that pay better than cane. Thus, several factors affect the quantity of sugar produced in a country, which are beyond the scope of this study.

In sub-Saharan Africa, sugar is only produced from sugarcane since there are no beet farms. Also, the fuel ethanol sector is not as prominent as in other parts of the world, and therefore, nearly all the sugarcane is used as raw material for sugar production. The rate of mechanization and fertilizer application is also fairly stable over the short to medium term. Hence, the yearly variations in crop outturn can directly be attributed to acreage increase and weather effects, among other issues that influence sugarcane yields, sucrose content, and total cane output. The area under sugarcane in South Africa, the Kingdom of Eswatini, and most of southern Africa have been fairly constant year-on-year over the past decade. In Kenya and most of East Africa, the cane acreage has risen consistently in the past five years. There are other variables that affect sugar production in various jurisdictions, most of which cannot be effectively quantified in the precincts of this study. Thus, we utilized a model that considers total annual

output as a function of past years’ production quantity to forecast cane sugar production.

Despite its prowess, dynamic updating of functional time series has not been widely implemented in predicting crop production quantities. This study proposes three methods for developing a dynamic updating functional time series model to improve sugar production forecasting in African countries. The proposed techniques are ridge regression (RR), penalized least squares (PLS), and local polynomial regression (LPR).

METHODOLOGY

2.1 Choice of the Study Area

Production conditions differ in various locations across the region. In East Africa, sugar milling happens all year in most countries, while in southern Africa, most sugarcane harvesting and processing happens between April and December. Also, in some producer states, the crop is fully irrigated, and cane development is more mechanized. Therefore, this study intends to use data from Kenya, South Africa, and Eswatini, representing the varied nature of the sugar production landscape within Sub-Saharan Africa. South Africa, the continent’s largest cane sugar producer, harvests and processes most of its cane between April and December. Most of the years, almost no sugar manufacturing happens in the off-crop season, and both small and large-scale farmers contribute significantly to the total output. Eswatini, currently Africa’s fifth-most significant cane sugar producer (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2023), experiences weather and crop calendar similar to South Africa’s. However, unlike South Africa, the sugarcane crop in Eswatini is almost fully irrigated. Again, both Eswatini and South Africa are net sugar exporters. Kenya, Africa’s third most significant cane sugar producer, is a sugar deficit country located within the equatorial region and produces sugar throughout the calendar year. The weather pattern is significantly different from that of southern Africa; the crop

is almost fully rainfed, and cane development is completely in the hands of small-scale farmers with an average of 0.8 hectares each (Agriculture and Food Authority, 2023). Most of the East African sugar-producing countries share experiences similar to Kenya’s. Therefore, the three countries selected for this study fairly represent the overall experiences in sugarproducing nations within Sub-Saharan Africa.

2.2 Dynamic Updating Models

One of the main interests in statistical modeling is the ability to forecast the values of a given dataset using the available information. Fewer observations make a model more rigid, and thus, it is advisable to use as much data as possible. However, adding more historical data to the model results in a well-known challenge, especially when dealing with non-parametric statistics because of the exponential decay of estimates. This challenge is overcome by functional ideas, enabling users to build models incorporating more data. For a univariate time series, the data is split into curves for every time continuum. For example, suppose monthly data is recorded for several years. In that case, each year is regarded as a single curve instead of 12 discrete data points, which enables like-for-like comparison of yearly experiences.

The main goal of dynamic updating is to improve the point forecast accuracy of sequentially observed time series. When the overall time range is split into several time intervals, each containing a number of data points, the final curve may contain incomplete observations. Let $X_i(t)$ denote the complete set of observations for monthly sugar production totals for the i th year (that is the production totals from January to December). Also, let t_{m_0} denote the time in months corresponding to the last available observation of the most current yearly curve.

Then, the observed part of the current yearly curve is given in equation (1)

$$X_{(n+1)}(t_e) = [X_{(n+1)}(t_1), \dots, X_{(n+1)}(t_{m_0})]^T \tag{1}$$

The primary goal is to forecast sugar production quantities for the remainder of the year $n + 1$, denoted as $X_{(n+1)}$. The unobserved part of the current year’s monthly sugar output is represented as;

$$X_{(n+1)}(t_i) = [X_{(n+1)}(t_{m_0+1}), \dots, X_{(n+1)}(t_p)]^T \tag{2}$$

and the estimate thereof as;

$$\hat{X}_{(n+1)}(t_i) = [\hat{X}_{(n+1)}(t_{m_0+1}), \dots, \hat{X}_{(n+1)}(t_p)]^T \tag{3}$$

where l denotes the remaining time length in months. New data is added to the prediction model every time an observation is made to improve the accuracy of the forecast. The unobserved part of the curve was estimated using LPR, PLS, and RR methods discussed previously in section 3.3. FPCA was used to select the months that explain at least 80 percent of the variation from the average production for the

respective unobserved period considered in the prediction methodologies. The results obtained from the three techniques were compared with those obtained using Hyndman and Khandakar (2008) automatic ARIMA algorithm.

2.3 Functional Principal Component Analysis

The dynamic functional principal component (FPCA) scores were obtained using the kernel estimator provided by Shang

(2020). The method uses Karhunen-Loeve expansion to break down stochastic process Y as follows.

$$Y(u) = \mu(u) + \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \alpha_i \phi_i(u) \tag{4}$$

where $\mu(u)$ is the mean function and α_i is a standard normal random variable. The FPCA scores α_i are obtained by projecting $Y(u) - \mu(u)$ towards the j th eigenfunction ϕ_i .

The researchers performed functional principal component analysis (FPCA) in the following steps:

1. Construct the mean function $\mu(u)$ by calculating the average monthly production up to year n .

$$\mu(u) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i$$

2. Center the data by subtracting the mean function $\mu(u)$ from each monthly output curve:

$$\hat{Y}_i(u) = Y_i - \mu(u)$$

Centering ensures that the analysis focuses on deviations from a typical pattern over time.

3. Estimate the principal component scores (α_i) by projecting the centered data onto the Fourier series basis function (ϕ_i) and using the eigenvectors and eigenvalues from the variance-covariance matrix.
4. Determine the number of functional principal components (FPC) to retain using the scree test and by cross-validation. The selected FPCs best represents the data variability along each principal component.
5. Examine the principal components and the corresponding eigenfunctions to interpret the variability patterns in the underlying data.

The current study retained functional principal components that explain at least 80% of the total variation in each dataset. Based Jolliffe (2002) analysis, PCs that cumulatively account for 80% of the total observed variance are sufficient to represent a dataset’s important characteristics.

2.4 Estimating the Remaining Part of the Curve Using Penalized Least Squares

The PLS method is an improvement of the OLS technique. It introduces a penalty for each of design provides a balance between the goodness of fit and complexity and is useful in covariate selection (Bunea et al., 2011). Under the PLS methodology, annual production (Y) can be modeled as;

$$f_{\lambda}(Y_i) = \theta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^n \theta_j Y_{i-1} + \sum_{j=1}^n \delta_j B_j(Y) \tag{5}$$

where B_j is the basis function dependent on Y_{i-1} , θ_0 is a constant term, θ_j and δ_j are coefficients, and $Y = [Y_1, \dots, Y_n]^T$. Assuming a Fourier Series basis function, $B_j(Y_{i-1}) =$

$$\sin\left(\frac{j\pi Y_{i-1}}{p}\right) \text{ or } B_j(Y_{i-1}) = \cos\left(\frac{j\pi Y_{i-1}}{p}\right),$$

where p is the period of the function, in this case, the number of production months in a year.

Also, it is possible to estimate a point (x_{ij}) within the curve (Y_i), which is akin to estimating the total output in month x_{ij} within year Y_i . Let matrix X be the monthly sugar production where x_{ij} is the production total for the j th month in the i th year.

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1p} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{n1} & x_{n2} & \dots & x_{np} \end{bmatrix}$$

The row sums in the above matrix represent the yearly total output Y_i . The column averages corresponding to the mean production for months 1,2,...,p will be calculated as:

$$\mu_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} \tag{6}$$

From equation (5), calculate the B_j coefficients for estimating the remaining part of the current curve as follows.

$$\hat{B}_j^{PLS} = H Y_{n+1,e}^{\wedge} \tag{7}$$

where H is the hat matrix and $Y_{n+1,e}^{\wedge}$ is the mean adjusted estimate. The hat matrix H is obtained as;

$$H = X_c^*(X_c^{*T} X_c^*)^{-1} X_c^{*T} \tag{8}$$

where X_c^* is the adjusted design matrix. The predicted total sugar production for the remaining months of the year is then given by;

$$Y_{n+1|n,l}^{PLS} = E[Y_{n+1,l}|I_l, \Phi_l] = O_{m0} + \hat{\phi}_{1,l} \hat{\beta}_{1,n+1} + \dots + \hat{\phi}_{p^*,l} \hat{\beta}_{k,n+1} \tag{9}$$

where β_k is the selected principal component and ϕ_i is the FPCA score, l is the remaining duration in months, and O_{m0} is the observed part of the production year. The term $\hat{\phi}_{i,l} \hat{\beta}_{k,n+1}$ represents the estimated sugar output for month i of year $n+1$ and $1 \leq i \leq p^*$. In this case p^* is the last production month in the current year. The PLS corresponds to RR at L2 regularization.

Note: Similar to the PLS, the Ridge Regression (RR) penalizes the OLS coefficients that deviate significantly from zero. The RR model minimizes a penalized error sum of

$$Y_i = m(Y_{i-1}) + v(Y_{i-1})^{\frac{1}{2}} \epsilon_i \tag{10}$$

where ϵ_i is an independent and identically distributed standard normal random variable representing the error term; $v(\cdot)$ is the variance function; and $m(\cdot)$ is the function whose

estimate is desired. New data $Y_{n+1,e}$ is added to the model, and the model coefficients B_j are obtained by minimizing the residual sum of squares. For a particular point c , the model coefficients can be obtained from the kernel estimator of the regression equation;

$$\hat{m}(c; q, h) = e_1^T (X_c^{*T} W_c^* X_c^*)^{-1} X_c^{*T} W_c^* Y^* = e_1^T \hat{B}_j(c) \tag{11}$$

Matrices X and Y have been adjusted to contain sugar production values corresponding to the unobserved period l , giving X_c^* and Y^* , respectively. The original response set used for kstep forecasting is $Y = [Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_n]^T$ where Y_i is the total sugar production in i^{th} year.

However, for dynamic updating predictions, the response set is adjusted by subtracting the observed months' production from the yearly total as;

$$Y_i^* = Y_i - O_{m0} \tag{12}$$

leading to the adjusted response set $Y^* = [Y_1^*, Y_2^*, \dots, Y_n^*]^T$ corresponding to the unobserved period l . The adjusted design X_c^* is, therefore, made up of elements obtained using the lagged values of Y^* .

Also, predict the FPCA scores $\hat{\phi}_l$ using the LPR methodology in equation (11) and $q = 3$. The most suitable order of the local polynomial is achieved through cross validation to obtain the degree that gives the lowest MAPE value on the training and testing samples. The resulting scores for the retained principal components β_k give the ultimate forecast for the partially observed current year given in equation (13).

$$Y_{n+1|n,l}^{LPR} = E[Y_{n+1,l}|I_l, \Phi_l] = O_{m0} + \hat{\phi}_{1,l} \hat{\beta}_{1,n+1} + \dots + \hat{\phi}_{p^*,l} \hat{\beta}_{k,n+1} \tag{13}$$

O_{m0} is the observed part of the current curve and $Y_{n+1|n,l}^{LPR}$ is the sugar production total for the current year given information for time length l is still unobserved.

The results obtained from dynamically updating the LPR, RR, and PLS models are then compared with those of the ARIMA model, the most widely adopted prediction method used in the industry. The Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average Model of order p is expressed as ARIMA (p,d,q)(P,D,Q)_s where p is the order of the non-seasonal autoregressive (AR) part, d is the degree of non-seasonal differencing, and q is the order of the non-seasonal moving average (MA) part. Also, P is the order of the seasonal AR, D is the degree of seasonal differencing, Q is the order of the seasonal MA, and s is the seasonal period. Ideally for a random variable y_t , an ARIMA (p,d,q)(P,D,Q)_s can be expressed using backshift and differencing operators as;

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$$\Phi(B). \Phi_s(B^s). \Delta^D. \Delta^D_s. y_t = \Theta(B). \Theta_s(B^s). \epsilon_t \quad (14)$$

New data points are added, and a fresh forecast is generated each time an additional observation is made.

2.6 Evaluating Forecast Accuracy

The proposed models were evaluated using the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). MAPE is robust to outliers since it gives the error margins as percentages rather than absolute deviations. MAPE is also scale-independent and sensitive to forecast accuracy, making it suitable for predicting large values and comparing datasets with varying magnitudes. The technique that results in a lower MAPE produces more accurate forecasts. It is calculated as follows:

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{Y_i - \hat{Y}_i}{Y_i} \right| \times 100\% \quad (15)$$

where:

- n is the sample size.
- Y_i is the observation at time i .
- \hat{Y}_i is the predicted value at time i .
- $\left| \frac{Y_i - \hat{Y}_i}{Y_i} \right| \times 100\%$ calculates the absolute percentage error for each observation.

The precision level of the resulting predictions were categorized according to Lewis (1982) MAPE judgment scale

as highly accurate (below 10%), good (between 11% and 20%), and reasonable (21% to 50% and poor (above 50%).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Dataset

This study analyzed 34 years of sugar production data obtained from the International Sugar Organization (ISO), Eswatini Sugar Association (ESA), and the Agriculture and Food Authority (Kenya). The prominent features of the data are shown in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1: Annual Sugar Output in Metric Tons (1990 to 2023)

Country	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Median
Eswatini	586,971	77,887	413,945	746,981	594,921
Kenya	499,024	98,254	328,844	796,554	489,603
South Africa	2,119,434	363,183	1,259,208	2,844,165	2,121,366

Figure 1: Yearly sugar production curves

From figure 1, it is evident that sugar output is lowest at the start of the milling season in April and towards the end of the production season in December in both Eswatini and South Africa. The rainfall season in the two countries begin in October and end in April, with December, January, and February being the wettest months. Therefore, the slow start in April is partly because the ground is still normally wet, which does not favor cane harvesting and transportation. Also, most of the time factories do not begin milling on the first date of the season, reducing the crushing period in April. In December, the cane milling pace reduces due to wet weather and decreased cane supply. Towards the end of the milling season, most of the mature sugarcane has been harvested and processed, leaving little feedstock for the mills. In Figure 1, the few cases when the yearly sugar production curve spikes in December are usually due to extended milling season, where harvesting continues into the typical off-crop period (January to March). Still, most the sugar in Eswatini and South Africa is produced between May and November, with the peak production months being July, August, and September. Unlike Eswatini, where nearly all sugarcane farms are irrigated, only a quarter of South Africa’s sugarcane fields are under irrigation, leaving about three-quarters under

rainfed agriculture. South African sugar production has a higher volatility compared to Eswatini’s experience due to increased exposure to adverse weather, especially drought conditions.

On the other hand, Kenyan sugar factories operate throughout the year with no off-crop season. The sugarcane crop is grown almost fully under rainfed agriculture. It is possible to spot from Table 1 and Figure 1 that Kenya’s sugarcane sector has the highest volatility among the three cases under study, mainly due to the increased risk of the adverse effects of drought. The country’s sugar output tends to drop in the April-May period, while March records the highest sugar production in most of the years. At the peak of the long rain season in April-May, some factories opt to take a break and conduct machinery maintenance exercises. The heavy rainfall, and in some cases flooding in the cane belt, makes it difficult to harvest and transport efficiently. As the fields dry up, monthly sugar production quantities begin to rise at around the July-August period.

The study utilized the functional principal components that explain at least 80 percent of the total variation, which according to Jolliffe (2002) are a sufficient representation for analysis.

Figure 2: Cumulative variance explained by FPC combinations at the onset

In all three cases, three functional principal components (FPC) were sufficient the onset (after observing the first two months of the milling season). For example, Figure 2 shows a scree plot of the proportion of total variation explained by the all the possible functional principal component combinations for the Kenyan data.

As the unobserved part of the year becomes shorter, the number of FPCs required to explain

80 percent proportion of the total variation for the same dataset gradually becomes smaller. For instance, from Figure2, the number of FPCs required for the Eswatini sugar dataset having observed the first six months of production up

to September (75 percent of the milling season) reduces to one. Table 2 summarizes the number of FPC used for each of the three datasets for the particular stages of estimation. It is generally assumed that to conduct dynamic updating, at least two months of the current year must have been observed. Hence, the research intentionally omitted the periods February-December for Kenya and May to December for Eswatini and South Africa. A January to December period for Kenya or April to December for Eswatini and South Africa would constitute forecasting of an entire season’s production, already covered in Agwingi et al. (2024).

Table 2: Functional Principal Components Required to Explain 80% of the Total Variation

Unobserved Period	Eswatini	Kenya	South Africa
Mar-Dec	-	3	-
Apr-Dec	-	3	-
May-Dec	-	3	-
Jun-Dec	3	2	3
Jul-Dec	3	2	3
Aug-Dec	3	2	3
Sep-Dec	2	1	2

Oct-Dec	2	1	1
Nov-Dec	1	1	1
Dec+	-	-	-

3.2 Dynamic Updating Forecasts Using Select Models

For the sake of ranking, a model that provides the highest number of highly accurate forecasts (MAPE values below 10%) for the time steps within the production season is considered the most suitable for predicting the outcomes for

the specific case. However, a technique that does not give the most number of highly accurate predictions in a given set, may be considered appropriate for forecasting only for the particular time period(s) where it is superior (has the lowest MAPE).

Table 3: Select Dynamic Updating Models Based on Average MAPE

Unobserved	Country	LPR	RR	PLS
Jun-Dec	Eswatini	8.1622	6.5500	5.9999
Jul-Dec		9.2894	7.8953	6.4497
Aug-Dec		9.6772	8.3024	8.3190
Sep-Dec		9.4968	8.2081	8.3224
Oct-Dec		10.8177	9.3264	10.3897
Nov-Dec		5.7709	5.1540	6.5733
Dec				
Mar-Dec	Kenya			
Apr-Dec		20.4965	21.3182	12.8957
May-Dec		18.4544	19.6912	12.3397
Jun-Dec		15.8975	16.9896	11.4774
Jul-Dec		13.3074	14.0247	9.9336
Aug-Dec		10.3571	10.9769	8.4197
Sep-Dec		8.0343	8.5680	6.7510
Oct-Dec		6.2663	6.7883	5.4461
Nov-Dec		3.8941	4.2314	3.5805
Dec		1.9849	2.0163	1.5326
Jun-Dec	South Africa	6.9074	8.7880	8.3685
Jul-Dec		6.3693	8.4376	6.9281
Aug-Dec		3.6912	6.3180	4.0054
Sep-Dec		1.6373	3.9495	2.1923
Oct-Dec		1.8040	3.7679	1.7763
Nov-Dec		1.6445	1.4736	1.5939
Dec+		1.6420	1.4266	1.5225

From Table 3, the ridge regression (RR) dynamic updating model is the most suitable among all the three techniques

proposed for estimating the unobserved part of the current season’s production total for Eswatini. The RR technique

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provides precise forecasts throughout the crop year, giving accuracy levels of between 91% and 96%. However, the PLS updating method edged out RR technique for the first two possible periods of interest, June - December and July - December. Whereas RR is the best overall model, it is worth also implementing the PLS dynamic updating when forecasting for June-December and July-December timelines.

Using the RR dynamic updating methodology, the researchers predicted the monthly and seasonal total of Eswatini’s sugar output for 2020. From the data obtained, which covers 1990 to 2022, the 2020 season was the latest crop year, with a milling season that spanned exactly nine months, as per the assumptions of the current study. The results are shown in table 4.

Table 4: Ridge Regression Test Forecast of Eswatini’s Sugar Production for 2020

	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec+	Estimated Production (Y)	MAPE
Actual Production	83,996	121,730	101,835	116,785	86,954	48,577	11,388	-	-
Predicted Values									
Jun-Dec	89,550	102,599	99,682	96,691	90,190	74,945	32,333	699,288	2.1510
Jul-Dec	-	95,611	95,398	93,238	90,662	82,251	40,270	694,724	1.4843
Aug-Dec	-	-	95,159	91,244	83,020	69,378	32,883	690,708	0.8977
Sep-Dec	-	-	-	87,132	80,924	67,039	33,989	689,943	0.7859
Oct-Dec	-	-	-	-	77,993	64,428	34,084	714,149	4.3219
Nov-Dec	-	-	-	-	-	56,499	30,105	711,202	3.8914
Dec	-	-	-	-	-	-	30,105	703,280	2.7342

* Note: Total actual sugar output in 2020 was 684,563 tons. Overall output up to the end of May was 113,298 tons.

For a normal season (nine months of milling), the total yearly output can be predicted with high precision. The results show that the RR dynamic updating model can produce predictions that are between 96% and 99% accurate when applied for a standard sugar milling season in Eswatini. The number of essential FPCs declined to one and zero at the beginning of November and December since it is believed that only two

months and one month of the milling season are unobserved, respectively (see Table 2). Hence, the error margins are higher for extended seasons than the usual nine-month production year. Table 5 is the test prediction for monthly output and annual total production for South Africa in 2022 using the LPR dynamic updating method.

Table 5: Local Polynomial Regression Test Forecast of South Africa’s Sugar Production for 2022

	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec+	Estimated Production (Y)	MAPE
Actual Production	277,552	250,022	321,075	243,149	224,134	163,206	154,909	-	-
Predicted Values									
Jun-Dec	276,702	296,798	322,707	266,305	240,826	178,198	116,165	1,989,654	3.3050
Jul-Dec	-	296,759	324,735	264,550	240,613	177,816	116,271	1,990,249	3.3359
Aug-Dec	-	-	318,627	269,455	235,516	178,319	117,372	1,938,816	0.6654
Sep-Dec	-	-	-	269,291	239,803	180,846	114,239	1,944,781	0.9751

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Oct-Dec	-	-	-	-	239,567	183,863	114,019	1,921,200	0.2492
Nov-Dec	-	-	-	-	-	176,646	121,784	1,906,315	1.0221
Dec	-	-	-	-	-	-	121,784	1,892,875	1.7199

Note. Total actual sugar production in 2022 was 1,926,000 tons. Overall output up to the end of May was 291,953 tons.

Results from Table 3 show that the LPR dynamic updating method is the most suitable of the three proposed techniques for estimating South Africa’s sugar output. From Table 5, it is evident that LPR gives highly accurate projections ranging from about 97% with only two months observed to 99% precision with one month of the milling season remaining. Despite its prowess in modeling the South Africa case, the

accuracy of the LPR dynamic updating technique reduces when the sugar milling continues undeterred into the January-March period. Still, the model’s precision level did not fall below 90% on the test sample from the 2021 crop year. Table 6 is the test forecast of Kenya’s monthly and annual sugar production for 2020 using the PLS dynamic updating method.

Table 6: Penalized Least Squares Test Forecast of Kenya’s Sugar Production for 2021

	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Estimated MAPE Production (Y)	
Actual Production	66,326	58,444	57,651	59,226	57,276	64,244	45,348	49,869	59,467	62,514	-	-
	Pre dicted es Val											
Mar-Dec	56,383	49,529	48,340	50,207	49,074	49,329	48,744	48,500	46,563	44,880	611,425	12.6836
Apr-Dec	-	47,994	47,377	49,930	49,444	49,795	49,130	48,544	45,995	44,193	618,604	11.6584
May-Dec	-	-	42,904	48,882	48,819	49,172	49,598	48,715	46,584	44,772	624,092	10.8747
Jun-Dec	-	-	-	44,915	48,523	50,265	50,053	48,559	45,373	44,121	634,106	9.4446
Jul-Dec	-	-	-	-	44,365	48,454	49,100	48,485	45,909	45,224	643,060	8.1659
Aug-Dec	-	-	-	-	-	46,011	48,018	47,836	45,501	45,294	651,459	6.9665
Sep-Dec	-	-	-	-	-	-	46,664	47,385	45,968	46,002	669,062	4.4526
Oct-Dec	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	45,921	45,379	45,738	665,429	4.9714
Nov-Dec	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	42,675	43,915	664,850	5.0541
Dec	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	43,915	681,642	2.6561

* Note: Total actual sugar production in 2021 was 700,241 tons. Overall output up to the end of February was 119,876 tons.

The PLS dynamic updating method produces better results than the other two techniques for estimating the unobserved part of the current year’s output in Kenya. Based on Lewis (1982) MAPE judgment scale, LPR gives good forecast for the first three possible periods (Mar-Dec, Apr-Dec, and May-

Dec), but only manages to generate highly accurate predictions after observing five production months. The average error margin ranges between 2.6561% and 12.6836 % and reduces consistently with each additional month observed.

3.3 Dynamic Updating Using the Auto-ARIMA Model

The automatic ARIMA dynamic updating model MAPE results are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Auto-ARIMA Dynamic Updating MAPE Results

Unobserved	Kenya	Eswatini	South Africa
Mar-Dec	36.49	-	-
Apr-Dec	27.66	-	-
May-Dec	18.35	-	-
Jun-Dec	10.41	9.19	6.17
Jul-Dec	6.15	11.14	4.54
Aug-Dec	2.55	12.79	3.50
Sep-Dec	3.25	12.82	2.72
Oct-Dec	3.34	13.97	2.33
Nov-Dec	9.93	8.32	1.86
Dec	3.02	4.50	1.77

The auto-ARIMA updating method had the largest error margins of all the models used to estimate the unobserved segment of Kenya’s current year. In particular, the technique yields MAPE values ranging from 36.4949% to 3.0223%, translating to 63.5% to 97% forecast accuracy. For the Kenyan case, the auto-ARIMA dynamic updating requires the user to have observed at least four months of production to attain good predictions. Highly accurate forecasts are only achievable after observing half of the crop year (6 months of output).

However, when applied to the South African data, the automatic ARIMA results were highly accurate for all the

possible updating periods. The error margin consistently reduced from

6.1652% after observing two months of the milling season to 1.7677% at the start of December. Therefore, the ARIMA technique gives precise predictions with accuracy levels of between 94% and 98% on the South African dataset.

Lastly, the auto-ARIMA dynamic updating resulted in three precise predictions out of the seven estimation periods on the Eswatini sugar data. For the majority of the milling season, the model produced good predictions (MAPE between 11% and 20%).

Figure 3: Eswatini - Dynamic Updating MAPE

From Figure 3, the RR dynamic updating is the most suitable technique for Eswatini’s case. RR produces highly accurate forecasts for most of the milling season from August onwards. However, the PLS is appropriate when applied at the onset, having observed two or three months of output. Again, all the three proposed techniques performed better than the autoARIMA in modeling the Eswatini data. When applied to the Kenyan dataset, the auto-ARIMA dynamic updating estimates are erratic at the start of the sugar milling season. On the other hand, the PLS yields good predictions of the current year’s total output in the early months of the season when less data is available. In comparison, PLS and auto-ARIMA give an equal number of the lowest MAPE values (best forecast) across the possible updating periods. Still, the PLS updating technique is an appropriate choice since the model’s precision consistently increases as more data is added.

All the models, including the automatic ARIMA dynamic updating, produced highly accurate estimates of the unobserved part of the current year’s output for the South African case. The ARIMA technique gives more precise results during the onset after observing 2-4 months of the

sugar milling season. Thereafter, both the PLS and LPR models produced more accurate predictions than the auto-ARIMA.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

At least one of the three proposed methods (LPR, RR, and PLS) produced was more suitable than the auto-ARIMA for each dataset. Only when estimating the unobserved part of the current year for the Kenyan sugar industry did the ARIMA methodology match the PLS for the number of best predictions produced (lowest MAPE per period). Still, the functional techniques (LPR, RR, and PLS) produced more consistent accuracy levels in all cases and were preferred for dynamic updating.

For Eswatini, the RR was the best overall model for estimating the season total for a partially observed year, whereas the PLS and LPR dynamic updating techniques were preferred for

Kenya and South Africa, respectively. The selected models produced highly accurate South Africa and Eswatini sugar output predictions across possible estimation periods. For the Kenyan data, the chosen PLS dynamic updating technique

gives good forecasts when applied during the first half of the season and highly accurate predictions when implemented during the second half. Because of the constant season length in Kenya, the precision level increased consistently as more months were observed, and new data was added to the dynamic updating model.

Dynamic updating gives a timely opportunity to review and improve a largely erroneous prediction made before the season starts. The possibility of refining the production forecast with only a few months of the season observed is critical because it enables stakeholders to realign their strategies.

The study recommends that methods of forecasting annual crop production quantities be used together with dynamic updating models to improve forecast accuracy when dealing with highly volatile datasets. Even for the less volatile trends, it is reasonable to implement dynamic updating prediction models for cross-checking the performance of the yearly forecasts during the season.

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